

TEXT TYPES AND DIFFERENT STYLES OF WRITING

Teshayeva Maftuna

2nd course masters' degree student

English language and literature major

Navai State Pedagogical Institute

Abstract In general, the linguistic features examined by writing researchers fall into three large constructs: lexical, syntactic, and cohesion. Language features are also important elements of identifying discourse structures as well (i.e., claims, arguments, theses, and rhetorical moves), but the language structures used in these determinations may not be linguistic in nature per se and are not the focus of this overview. Instead, this review will focus on research that has examined links between writing quality/development and linguistic features as found in text, especially those features related to lexical sophistication, syntactic complexity, and text cohesion. These differences will be covered in the discussion section of this paper.

Key words: text, cohesion, text types, narrative text, factual text, literary text.

There are many different text types a person may encounter in the course of a single day. They might read a newspaper article in the morning, then write a letter (or email) to a friend, follow a recipe to make dinner, complete an application form, pick up a leaflet, before finally savoring a good novel at bedtime. While all of these forms of text have the written word in common, each has its own unique features and conventions.

There are many different ways to categorize the broad range of reading and writing materials we can encounter in a single day. But, generally speaking, it's helpful to think of them in terms of two overarching and broad categories: factual and literary.

Factual texts. Endeavor to inform, instruct, or persuade through the use of facts and information.

Literary texts. Seek to entertain, enlighten, or elicit emotion through a creative use of language and structure.

Within each of these two broad categories are several sub-categories, which we will explore in the rest of this article. Take note, depending on the curriculum you are working with, text types may be referred to using slightly differing terms. It's worth noting, too, that while the two general categories are a very useful way to think about the different text types, not all text types will sit exclusively in one camp or the other. For example, the increasingly common genre known as literary nonfiction, or creative nonfiction, has a foot in both camps. That said, for the vast majority of text types that our students will look at, these categories are functional and practical. Now, let's take a closer look at some of these text types. We'll start with the factual.

Discussion texts. *Purpose:* The purpose of a discussion text is to explore more than one point of view on a given subject in order to reach an informed opinion or to make a decision on an issue.

Structure: Generally speaking, discussion texts will begin by providing background information on the issue before introducing the central area or areas of contention. At this point, the text will then begin to explore the various arguments for and against with an examination of the supporting evidence. The conclusion will summarize both sides of the argument before giving a recommendation based on the writer's evaluation of those arguments.

Main Features:

- The title is often in the form of a question
- Written in the present tense.
- Generic statements are followed by specific examples
- Arguments are sometimes supported by diagrams, illustrations etc.

Explanatory texts. *Purpose:* Explanatory texts move beyond providing straightforward descriptions to looking at things like causes and reasons. They move beyond retelling what happened, such as in a simple report, to address the why and how of what happened.

Structure: Explanatory texts usually open with a general statement that introduces the topic to be explored, for example, “During the winter, some birds migrate to warmer parts of the world.” The various steps of the process are then explained in a logical order.

Main Features:

- The title reveals what is being explained
- It may contain diagrams, flowcharts, illustrations etc.
- Written in simple present tense.
- Time connectives are used such as first, after, then, next, finally etc.
- Talks to the reader directly, e.g. “You’ll be surprised to learn....”

Instructional / procedural texts. *Purpose:* Instructions and procedural texts communicate rules or processes to follow. They are commonly found in games, household appliances, recipes, etc. While, in some ways, instructional/procedural texts are similar to explanatory texts, the main difference is that while instructional/procedural texts tell you what to do, explanatory texts describe something.

Structure: This type of text begins with a defined objective or goal, which will often form the title. Usually, a list of resources, equipment etc., will be included, followed by a step-by-step description of the process to achieve the desired outcome. Often, the written process will be supported by diagrams and/or illustrations. Occasionally, the diagrams or illustrations may replace the written text entirely.

Main Features:

- The title indicates the process described, e.g. How to...
- Includes resource / equipment list

- The process is described step-by-step using bullet points, numbers etc
- Time connectives are used to organize writing (first, next, then, finally etc.)
- Imperatives used
- Diagrams / Illustrations are used to support or replace text.

Conclusion

Understanding the various aspects of the different writing genres will help students to navigate their way through writing that serves a broad range of purposes.

It will also help students in their own text compositions. Understanding the various underlying text structures will provide students with an effective means of organizing their work, helping to ensure their writing is fit for purpose.

Exposing your students to as many different genres as possible, and providing opportunities to explore how these text types operate, will go a long way to helping them develop into adaptive and organized readers and writers in the future.

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